

Digitization of workflow on manufacture and assembly elements integrated façade renovation

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Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is profoundly transforming the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry sector characterized by digital-driven approaches, enhanced collaboration, and standardization targeted towards the full life cycle of a built asset. One key aspect of this digitization paradigm is to examine prevailing workflows in the industry to improve data flow efficiency, foster standardization, and make technology accessible and open to stakeholders.

This research focuses on the manufacturing and assembly elements integrated within the facade renovation workflow with a case study application. The research commences by employing process models which are used to capture existing and proposed workflows that provide the foundation for the digitization strategy. The practical implementation of the strategy is explored using openBIM and open-source approaches. This includes generating Exchange Information Requirements, point cloud to BIM process automation, and collaboration guidelines.

openBIM and the use of open-source software solutions represent one of the directions for improving cooperation and data exchange in the discussed BIM processes. Open-source

software used in the research, e.g. Blender with BlenderBIM plugin, Ifcopenshell, etc. presents an interesting alternative to proprietary software and opens up new possibilities for the digitization of the construction industry.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/Yu6wyssxhkg>

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